

References

1. SAHADEV, R. K. SHARMA and S. K. SINDHWANI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 643.
2. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003; J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941, p. 298; H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; J. C. SULLIVAN, J. RYDBERG and W. F. MILLER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, **13**, 2023.
3. J. C. SULLIVAN, J. RYDBERG and F. MILLER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, **13**, 2059.
4. J. C. SULLIVAN and J. RYDBERG, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, **13**, 2023.
5. D. P. MELLOR and L. MALEY, *Nature (London)*, 1947, **159**, 370.
6. H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature (London)*, 1948, **162**, 746; *Analyst*, 1952, **77**, 813.
7. R. NASANEN and A. EKMAN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, **6**, 1389.
8. P. GEORGE and O. S. MCCLURE, *Prog. Inorg Chem.*, 1959, **1**, 428.
9. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations", Methuen, London, 1957, p. 82.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, New York, 1956, p. 177.
11. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of some Bivalent Metal Ions with (2/3/4-Carboxyphenyl) Diacetyl Monoxime in Water – Ethanol Medium

P. P. HANKARE^{*a}, M. B. CHAVAN^a, A. H. MANIKSHETE^b, R. S. RAMPURE^b and L. P. DESHMUKH^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Shivaji University Centre for P. G. Studies, Solapur-413 003

^cDepartment of Electronics, Shivaji University Centre for P. G. Studies, Solapur-413 003

Manuscript received 25 May 1992, revised 8 September 1992, accepted 17 September 1992

We report here the results of the formation of the complexes of divalent metal ions Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} with diacetyl monoxime and substituted carboxyanilines by pH-metric method of Irving and Rossotti¹ in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at $I=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) and at different temperatures.

Results and Discussion

The stabilities of the metal complexes of the ligands (i) DAMO-*o*-ABA, diacetylmonoxime *o*-aminobenzoic acid, (ii) DAMO-*m*-ABA, diacetylmonoxime *m*-aminobenzoic acid and (iii) DAMO-*p*-ABA, diacetylmonoxime *p*-aminobenzoic acid, depend on the magnitude of the acid dissociation constant of the ligand. These have been calculated by half-integral and graphical methods. The values of the average stability constants are given in Table 1. From the titration data, $\bar{n}_A$ values were calculated and plotted against pH to obtain values of pK_1 , pK_2 and pK_3 . These values were further corroborated by linear plots of $\log(1 - \bar{n}_A)/\bar{n}_A$, $\log(2 - \bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A - 1)$ and $\log(3 - \bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A - 2)$ vs pH. DAMO-*o*-ABA (1), DAMO-*m*-ABA (2) and DAMO-*p*-ABA (3) have two dissociable protons, therefore the formation curves extended over the range $2.99 > \bar{n}_A > 0.006$; the deviation being within 0.2 units. The pK values for compounds 1–3 are in the order, $3 > 2 > 1$.

These compounds have carboxyl substituent at *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-positions respectively. The observed pK values can be explained on the basis of electron-withdrawing inductive effect ($-I$) and electron-releasing mesomeric effect ($-M$). When the COOH group releases proton, the resulting carboxylate anion has ($+M$) electron-donating mesomeric effect. Since the mesomeric effect ($+M$) is not effective when the substituent is at *meta*-position the pK value of the compound should be lower than those of *ortho*- and *para*-substituted compounds. The observed value (10.75) of DAMO-*m*-ABA being less than that of DAMO-*p*-ABA, can be attributed to the electron-withdrawing inductive effect ($-I$) of the COOH group.

From the metal titration curve $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complexes as $\log K$. These are further corroborated by linear plots of $\log(1 - \bar{n})/\bar{n}$ against pL . The results agree within the ± 0.03 log units. The order of stability constants in metal complexes of the ligands has been found to be Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Mn^{II}, which is in good agreement with the order found by Irving and Williams².

The studies on the correlation of metal-ligand stabilities with atomic number and electronegativity, indicated that stability decreases with increasing

NOTES

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Ligand	Cation	Stability	Constant			ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		
			30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°
DAMO- <i>o</i> - ABA	H ⁺	log k_1	10.60	10.35	10.13	-61.07	-61.60	-62.22	-45.08	-42.29	-52.77	-52.77	-53.04	
	H ⁺	log k_2	5.80	5.60	5.35	-33.42	-33.33	-32.86	-36.07	-48.06	08.75	08.75	09.93	
	H ⁺	log k_3	3.45	3.29	3.10	-19.88	-19.58	-19.04	-28.85	-36.53	29.63	29.63	30.38	
	Cu ²⁺	log k_1	12.40	11.32	10.62	-71.44	-67.37	-65.23	194.76	134.57	407.00	407.00	401.04	
	Ni ²⁺	log k_1	11.10	9.78	8.84	-63.95	-58.21	-54.29	238.04	180.70	574.56	574.56	568.88	
	Co ²⁺	log k_1	10.28	9.14	10.10	-59.23	-54.40	-49.75	205.58	199.53	483.02	483.02	482.46	
	Zn ²⁺	log k_1	8.62	7.94	7.54	-49.66	-47.26	-46.31	122.63	-79.90	240.81	240.81	236.28	
	Mn ²⁺	log k_1	7.76	7.24	6.98	-44.71	-43.09	-42.87	-93.77	-49.98	161.93	161.93	157.60	
DAMO- <i>o</i> - ABA	H ⁺	log k_1^1	10.75	10.60	10.40	-61.94	-63.09	-63.88	-27.05	-28.45	115.14	115.14	114.01	
	H ⁺	log k_2	6.37	6.10	5.81	-36.70	-35.77	-35.68	-64.92	-38.45	93.14	93.14	90.52	
	H ⁺	log k_3	3.61	3.41	3.25	-20.80	-20.30	-19.96	-36.07	-30.76	50.39	50.39	49.86	
	Cu ²⁺	log k_1	12.76	11.30	10.64	-73.52	-67.25	-65.32	263.29	126.88	626.31	626.31	612.82	
	Ni ²⁺	log k_1	11.68	10.04	9.70	-67.29	-59.75	-59.58	-295.75	-65.36	753.98	753.98	711.19	
	Co ²⁺	log k_1	10.82	8.84	8.50	-62.32	-52.61	-52.21	-357.06	-65.36	972.69	972.69	943.84	
	Zn ²⁺	log k_1	10.20	7.70	7.50	-58.77	-45.83	-46.06	-450.84	-38.45	1293.97	1293.97	1253.18	
	Mn ²⁺	log k_1	9.56	7.08	6.90	-55.08	-42.14	-42.38	-447.23	-34.60	1294.23	1294.23	1253.42	
DAMO- <i>o</i> - ABA	H _L ⁺	log k_1	10.88	10.68	10.48	-62.69	-63.56	-64.37	-36.07	-38.45	-87.85	-87.85	-87.61	
	H ⁺	log k_2	6.63	6.30	6.05	-38.20	-37.50	-37.16	-59.51	-48.06	70.34	70.34	59.20	
	H ⁺	log k_3	3.73	3.52	3.29	-21.49	-20.95	-20.21	-37.87	-44.22	54.06	54.06	54.69	
	Cu ²⁺	log k_1	12.90	12.06	11.50	-74.32	-71.78	-70.63	-151.48	-107.65	254.65	254.65	250.31	
	Ni ²⁺	log k_1	11.80	10.90	10.18	-67.99	-64.87	-62.52	-162.30	-138.41	311.28	311.28	308.91	
	Co ²⁺	log k_1	10.28	9.60	9.30	-59.23	-57.14	-57.12	-122.63	-57.67	209.24	209.24	202.82	
	Zn ²⁺	log k_1	8.88	8.22	7.78	-51.16	-48.92	-47.78	-129.02	-84.59	223.96	223.96	220.55	
	Mn ²⁺	log k_1	8.04	7.46	7.24	-46.32	-44.40	-44.47	-104.598	-42.29	192.32	192.32	186.15	

basicity of the metal. Whereas the metal-ligand stability was found to decrease with increasing temperature (Table 1).

Experimental

Diacetylmonoxime and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids (Loba) and metal salts (AnalaR) were used. Ethanol was purified by standard procedure³. The ligands were synthesised by the reported procedure⁴. The purity of the ligands was checked by ir and m.p. All the solutions of the metal salts were prepared in double-distilled water.

The pH-metric titrations were carried out with the help of an Elico LT-120 pH-meter at three different temperatures (30, 40 and 50 ± 1°) in nitrogen atmosphere following the standard calibration procedures. The pH-readings in 50% ethanol-water

media were subjected to activity coefficient corrections⁵. The titration procedure and preparation of solutions were the same as described earlier⁶.

References

1. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
2. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1956, p. 177.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longmans, London, 1977, p. 835.
5. B. J. GUTBENZAHN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 565; R. G. BATES and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **38**, 699; R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 223.
6. C. K. BHASKAR, P. P. HANKAR and R. S. RAMPURE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 286.